

CLASSROOM CODE-SWITCHING ATTITUDES AMONG COLLEGE OF EDUCATION STUDENTS AT ISABELA STATE UNIVERSITY

Lorelyn L. Medico, Precious Joy V. Camaso, Precious Mae P. Lucas
Isabela State University-Echague Campus

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Abstract

Code-switching, the alternation between languages during communication, is a widespread practice in multilingual societies like the Philippines. Its role in academic settings has long been debated, with scholars questioning whether it enhances or hinders students' performance. However, there remains a gap in understanding how students' attitudes toward classroom code-switching relate to their scholastic achievement, particularly among teacher education students who are future classroom practitioners.

This study assessed the attitudes of College of Education students at Isabela State University-Echague campus toward classroom code-switching and examined its differences in their profile variables. Using a descriptive-survey design, data were collected through a structured questionnaire administered to students across year levels. The responses were analyzed using frequency counts, mean scores, and comparative statistical methods.

Subsequently, students generally perceive classroom code-switching as beneficial, aiding comprehension and facilitating classroom interaction. Female students emphasized their role in authentic self-expression, while second-year students associated it more strongly with honesty and emotional openness compared to other groups. Thus, while code-switching may not directly influence academic achievement, it contributes to inclusivity and expression, emphasizing its pedagogical value in higher education.

INTRODUCTION

The integration of the Bilingual Education Policy through Department Order No. 25, s. 1974 (DO 25) established English as the medium of instruction in science and mathematics, and Filipino in the social sciences and humanities. Its dual aim was to develop competence in both languages while advancing the intellectualization of the Filipino in line with the 1987 Constitution. In classroom practice, however, this policy often translates into code-switching, as teachers and students negotiate meaning across languages.

In essence, English, as a global lingua franca, offers access to science, technology, and international exchange (Nishanti, 2018), while the native language remains central to cultural and cognitive development. Within this bilingual framework, Taglish, Ilocano-English, and similar blends have become integral to classroom interaction—functioning as both a natural linguistic tendency and a pedagogical tool. Prior studies report that code-switching enhances comprehension and participation (Pefianco, 2006; Auer, 1998), yet others caution that it may hinder target language proficiency or create uneven standards (Sert, 2005; Macaro, 2009). This reflects ongoing debates in Philippine and ASEAN classrooms where multilingual realities shape learning.

Theoretically, this study draws not only on Selinker’s Interlanguage Theory (1972), which frames code-switching as part of learners’ interlanguage development, but also on contemporary perspectives such as sociocultural theory (Vygotsky, 1978), which situates language use as a mediating tool for learning, and translanguaging frameworks (Garcia & Wei, 2014), which view bilingual practices as dynamic resources rather than deficiencies. Interlinking these frameworks with student attitudes provides a richer lens for examining why learners accept or resist code-switching in academic spaces.

Despite ongoing debates, limited research systematically examines students’ attitudes toward code-switching and how these vary across demographic and academic profiles. While teachers’ practices are well-studied, students’ perspectives remain marginalized in language policy and pedagogy. Addressing this gap is crucial to clarify whether learners view code-switching as a support, a barrier, or a neutral practice in achieving communication and learning outcomes.

Accordingly, the present study investigates students’ attitudes toward classroom code-switching and explores how these attitudes vary according to gender, year level, course, and native language (L1). With such, it reframes the understanding of code-switching not only as a linguistic phenomenon but also as a pedagogical and policy concern. The findings aim to inform ongoing debates on bilingual education, offering insights into how classroom practices can better align with both the goals of DO 25 and the broader challenges of multilingual instruction in Philippine higher education.

METHODS

Research Design

This quantitative research utilized a descriptive-comparative design, which allows for a systematic account of students’ demographic profiles and attitudes toward code-switching. Specifically, the descriptive design was for profiling and summarizing attitudinal trends, while the comparative component was used to determine significant differences across the profile and code-switching attitudes among students in the College of Education. Furthermore, the study adopted a cross-sectional approach, collecting data at a single point in time to capture variations in attitudes without tracing longitudinal changes.

Respondents and Locale of the Study

The respondents of this study were undergraduate students from the College of Education (CED) at Isabela State University–Echague campus, with a total population of 1,442

officially enrolled across BEEd, BSEd, BPEd, and BTLEd programs. Using Slovin’s formula with a 95% confidence level and a population proportion of 0.5, a representative sample of 313 students was determined (Tejada & Punzalan, 2012).

Additionally, stratified random sampling was employed to ensure proportional representation by gender, year level, course, and native language (L1). The respondents were chosen as they were officially enrolled in the CED during the academic year 2021–2022. Subsequently, ISU–Echague serves a linguistically diverse student body, where Filipino, Ilocano, and other regional languages interact with English in academic discourse, providing a sociolinguistic context for the investigation of code-switching attitudes.

Table 1. Respondents of the Study

Respondents	Population Size	Sample Size	Percentage
Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd)	593	129	41.21
Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEEd)	352	76	24.28
Bachelor of Physical Education (BPEd)	245	53	16.94
Bachelor of Technical and Livelihood Education (BTLEd)	252	55	17.57
Total	1,442	313	100

Research Instrument

The structured questionnaire was adapted from Valerio (2015), who examined Filipino–English code-switching attitudes among students of Quirino State University. The tool has established content validity through expert review and construct validity, as it measures attitudinal dimensions toward languages, code-switching, and code-switchers. For the present study, the instrument was adapted to the ISU–Echague context, where Filipino and English serve as institutional media of instruction, while Ilocano and other vernaculars dominate home domains. The retention of Tagalog–English switching reflects the policy-driven bilingual framework rather than purely local vernacular practices.

Due to pandemic restrictions, pilot testing was not conducted; however, the questionnaire’s prior validation and successful application in a comparable state university context strengthened its appropriateness for this study. Furthermore, the questionnaire consisted of two sections, wherein section I gathered demographic information such as gender, year level, course, and native language. Meanwhile, section II measured attitudes toward code-switching and attitudes toward code-switchers. As such, responses were rated using a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree).

Data Gathering Procedure and Analysis

Prior to data collection, permission was secured from the Dean of the College of Education, ISU-Echague campus, through a formal request letter. With the assistance of class advisers, respondents were identified from the sampled classes. Informed consent was obtained digitally via class group chats (Messenger) and emails to ensure voluntary participation. The questionnaire, administered through Google Forms, required approximately 15 minutes to complete.

Moreover, responses were tabulated and analyzed using appropriate statistical tools. Frequency counts and percentages described respondents' profiles, while weighted means summarized item-level variations in attitudes toward classroom code-switching. Also, to test for group differences, one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was employed, as it is appropriate for comparing mean scores across more than two independent groups. Before analysis, assumptions of normality and homogeneity of variances were checked and found not to be violated.

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to ethical standards in educational research. As ISU had no ethics review board at the time, approval was obtained from the Dean of the College of Education. Participation was voluntary with informed consent secured digitally. Anonymity was ensured by excluding names or identifiers, while privacy and data security were protected through password-secured Google Forms and controlled access, with Messenger used only to distribute survey links.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the Respondents

Table 2 displays the demographic profile of the respondents in the study. This particularly exhibits their gender, year level, course, and native language (L1).

Table 2. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Profile of Respondents

Variables	Frequency (n=313)	Percent
Gender		
Male	55	17.6%
Female	225	71.9%
LGBTQIA+	33	10.5%
Year Level		
1st year	65	20.8%
2nd year	55	17.6%
3rd year	97	31.0%
4th year	96	30.7%
Course		
BEEd	76	23.2%
BPEd	53	16.2%
BSEd	128	39.1%
BTLEd	56	17.1%

Native Language		
Iloco	181	57.8%
Tagalog	100	31.9%
Ibanag	10	3.2%
Yogad	8	2.6%
Ayangan-Ifugao	7	2.2%
Itawes	4	1.3%
Gaddang	3	1.0%

Out of the 313 respondents from the College of Education, the majority were female (71.9%), reflecting the gendered composition of teacher education programs, while 17.6% were male and 10.5% identified as LGBTQIA+. In terms of year level, most were in higher years, with third-year (31.0%) and fourth-year students (30.7%) forming the largest groups, suggesting that many respondents had greater academic exposure and classroom experience.

Program distribution showed a predominance of BSEd students (39.1%), followed by BEEEd (23.2%), BTLEd (17.1%), and BPEd (16.2%), ensuring representation across majors that emphasize varied pedagogical orientations and language use. Linguistically, the group was diverse but predominantly Ilocano (57.8%) and Tagalog (31.9%), with smaller proportions of Ibanag, Yogad, Ayangan-Ifugao, Itawes, and Gaddang speakers. This demographic profile highlights not only the female-dominated character of education programs but also the multilingual reality of ISU-Echague classrooms, conditions that provide an important lens for interpreting students' attitudes toward classroom code-switching.

Attitudes toward Code-switching of the Respondents

The table below delineates the students' attitudes and practices toward code-switching in different contexts, such as conversations, classroom discussions, and group activities.

Table 2. Attitudes Toward Code-switching of the Respondents

Statements	Mean	Qualitative Description	Description for Code-Switching Attitudes
1. I converse with my friends using Tagalog and English during our casual conversation.	3.97	Agree	Moderately favorable
2. In my English subject, I speak my own dialect and switch to English from time to time.	3.54	Agree	Moderately favorable
3. As a routine, I mix English and my vernacular.	3.65	Agree	Moderately favorable
4. During classroom discussion, mixing vernacular language and English language is a good practice among students.	3.70	Agree	Moderately favorable
5. Mixing Tagalog and English can be a means of expressing oneself more easily and more accurately.	4.01	Agree	Moderately favorable
6. Using both Tagalog and English during class discussion makes the learning of English lessons easier and faster.	4.01	Agree	Moderately favorable

7. During group activities, I use a combination of my dialect and English because it is allowed by my teacher.	3.81	Agree	Moderately favorable
8. Combining my dialect and the English language is just natural because it is a linguistic trend being practiced by everyone.	3.81	Agree	Moderately favorable
9. In using technological gadgets in the school, I prefer using English and Tagalog.	3.94	Agree	Moderately favorable
Mean	3.83	Agree	Moderately favorable

It can be gleaned that generally agreed with all the statements regarding classroom code-switching, as shown by the weighted mean of 3.83, which indicates a moderately favorable attitude. This agreement posits that code-switching is a frequent and normalized practice among students.

Notably, the highest mean scores of 4.01 showed that respondents perceived mixing Tagalog and English as a way to express themselves more easily and comfortably. This suggests that code-switching facilitates clearer self-expression and that it makes the learning of English lessons faster. These results align with Ospanova et al. (2017), who stressed that code-switching helps learners simplify ideas and articulate thoughts when English-only communication becomes difficult. This finding resonates with Naha et al. (2018), who observed that proper code-switching aids comprehension, stimulates curiosity, and increases class participation.

However, these findings imply that not all students uniformly support code-switching. While most means indicate agreement, some students resist it or prefer English-only communication. Sociolinguistically, these reflect how students construct their identities as bilingual speakers, since they view code-switching as natural and beneficial, they validate it as a legitimate communicative strategy that bridges English learning and their vernacular identities. Hence, such attitudes affirm the Bilingual Education Policy enshrined in the 1987 Constitution, which promotes competence in both English and Filipino as media of instruction. Yet, tensions remain, as some see code-switching as a fallback or sign of limited proficiency, underscoring challenges for bilingual pedagogy (Simasiku et al. 2015).

Attitudes toward Code Switchers of the Respondents

The following table exhibits the students' attitudes and perceptions of code-switchers in relation to intelligence, communication skills, and academic achievement.

Table 3. Attitudes toward Code Switchers Respondents

Statements	Mean	Qualitative Description	Description for Code-Switching Attitudes
1. A student who explains purely in English is more intelligent than one who mixes Tagalog and English during brainstorming.	3.13	Slightly Agree	Neutral

2. If I talk to someone who frequently combines his dialect & English, I look at his manner of speaking as a "better speaker" compared to those who purely use his dialect to communicate.	2.74	Slightly Agree	Neutral
3. A student who combines Tagalog and English during recitation in his English subject is just being "honest and expressive" about what he really feels.	3.87	Agree	Moderately favorable
4. A student who mixes his dialects and English during brainstorming has poor communication skills.	3.51	Agree	Moderately favorable
5. Code-switchers are also achievers.	3.70	Agree	Moderately favorable
6. Code-switchers should be given additional speaking lessons/drills than those who speak English better.	2.58	Disagree	Neutral
7. As a region with several Ilocanos, additional subjects in English must be given by the school to lessen the difficulties in learning English.	3.54	Agree	Moderately favorable
8. Students from the province usually code-switch; unlike in urban places, most students are fluent in English.	2.61	Slightly Agree	Neutral
Mean	3.32	Slightly Agree	Neutral

Table 3 shows that the computed general mean of 3.32 indicates that respondents slightly agreed, reflecting neutral overall toward code-switchers, inferring both favorable and unfavorable perceptions. This suggests that while frequent switching between languages occurs, students still recognize that code-switchers can, to some extent, be achievers.

Additionally, more favorable responses included the view that students who switch between English and Tagalog during recitation are being honest and expressive, with a mean of 3.87, echoing Abad (2010)'s finding that code-switching lowers anxiety and encourages participation. The respondents further agreed, with a mean of 3.70, that code-switchers can be achievers, reinforcing Simasiku et al.'s (2015) claim that alternating languages aids comprehension and engagement.

On the contrary, less favorable perceptions also surfaced, as respondents agreed, with a mean score of 3.51, that code-switchers in brainstorming have poor communication skills. This contrasts with Mangila (2019), who showed in Filipino English classrooms that teachers use code-switching for several pedagogic functions, particularly for instruction, content acquisition, and facilitating understanding, not as a sign of poor ability. Such divergence

reveals students' ambivalence, wherein many recognize its benefits, yet others view English-only proficiency as the mark of competence. These mixed views matter in educational contexts. As future teachers, students may carry forward both the validation and the stigma attached to code-switching. Without critical engagement, they might discourage a practice that research shows can enhance comprehension, especially among linguistically diverse learners.

Difference in the Attitudes of Respondents toward Code-switching according to Gender

Table 4 demonstrates the differences in respondents' attitudes toward code-switching when grouped according to gender. This comparison highlights whether male, female, and LGBTQIA+ students differ significantly in their attitudes and practices of code-switching.

Table 4. Difference in the Attitudes of Respondents toward Code-switching according to Gender

Statements	Group Means			F-value	p-value
	Male	Female	LGBTQIA+		
1. I converse with my friends using Tagalog and English during our casual conversation.	3.93	3.97	4.00	0.11 ^{ns}	0.90
2. In my English subject, I speak my own dialect and switch to English from time to time.	3.45	3.56	3.58	0.40 ^{ns}	0.67
3. As a routine, I mix English and my vernacular language in my English subject because my professor allows me.	3.56	3.67	3.64	0.41 ^{ns}	0.67
4. During classroom discussion, mixing vernacular language and English language is a good practice among students.	3.65	3.70	3.79	0.29 ^{ns}	0.75
5. Mixing Tagalog and English can be a means of expressing oneself more easily and more accurately.	3.93	4.03	4.00	0.41 ^{ns}	0.66
6. Using both Tagalog and English during class discussion makes the learning of English lessons easier and faster.	4.02	4.02	3.97	0.06 ^{ns}	0.95
7. During group activities, I use a combination of my dialect and English because it is allowed by my teacher.	3.58 ^l	3.83	4.06 ^m	3.47 [*]	0.03
8. Combining my dialect and the English language is just natural because it is a linguistic trend being practiced by everyone.	3.71	3.82	3.91	0.65 ^{ns}	0.53
9. In using technological gadgets in the school, I prefer using English and Tagalog.	3.82	3.98	3.91	0.94 ^{ns}	0.39

Legend: m=Male; f=female; l=LGBTQIA+

Note: Letter in superscript indicates which group has a significant mean difference.

*Significant ^{ns} Not Significant

The analysis unveiled that LGBTQIA+ respondents were significantly more likely (M = 4.06; p = 0.03) to use both their dialect and English during group activities when teachers

allowed it. This indicates that code-switching serves not only as a linguistic tool but also as a social adaptation strategy. Consistent with Amandla (2018), such adjustment helps LGBTQIA+ individuals present themselves acceptably and engage more comfortably.

On the other hand, Alenezi (2016) found no gender-based differences in code-switching attitudes, as both male and female students viewed it positively for comprehension. The contradiction suggests that broader gender categories may overlook the nuanced experiences of LGBTQIA+ learners, for whom identity and classroom context shape language use differently. Hence, this outcome emphasizes that teachers' acceptance of code-switching can foster inclusivity, while also reminding educators to critically address how language practices intersect with identity in diverse classrooms.

Table 5. Difference in the Attitudes of Respondents toward Code Switchers according to Gender

Statements	Group Means			F-value	p-value
	Male	Female	LGBTQIA+		
1. A student who explains purely in English is more intelligent than one who mixes Tagalog and English during brainstorming.	3.20	3.12	3.09	0.14 ^{ns}	0.87
2. If I talk to someone who frequently combines his dialect & English, I look at his manner of speaking as a "better speaker" compared to those who purely use his dialect to communicate.	2.60	2.77	2.76	0.67 ^{ns}	0.51
3. A student who combines Tagalog and English during recitation in his English subject is just being "honest and expressive" about what he really feels.	3.64 ^f	3.95 ^m	3.76	3.24 [*]	0.04
4. A student who mixes his dialects and English during brainstorming has poor communication skills.	3.40	3.53	3.58	0.35 ^{ns}	0.71
5. Code-switchers are also achievers.	3.76	3.69	3.64	0.31 ^{ns}	0.73
6. Code-switchers should be given additional speaking lessons/drills than those who speak English better.	2.53	2.56	2.76	0.95 ^{ns}	0.39
7. As a region with several Ilocanos, additional subjects in English must be given by the school to lessen the difficulties in learning English.	3.53	3.54	3.61	0.10 ^{ns}	0.90
8. Students from the province usually code-switch; unlike in urban places, most students are fluent in English.	2.64	2.60	2.64	0.04 ^{ns}	0.96

Legend: m=Male; f=female; l=LGBTQIA+

Note: Letter in superscript indicates which group has a significant mean difference.

*Significant ^{ns} Not Significant

The data delineate that respondents were more likely than their male and LGBTQIA+ counterparts to believe that students who mix Tagalog and English during recitation are being honest and expressive, and this difference was statistically significant (M = 3.95; p = 0.04). This implies that females may view code-switching as an authentic form of self-expression, validating the role of language alternation in conveying emotions more effectively. In the same

manner, Kane (2020) similarly conveyed gender influences code-switching patterns—women more frequently engage in intra-sentential switching and use it expressively

In essence, these educational nuances infer that without critical reflection, these students may either validate or stigmatize code-switching, risking overgeneralization and reinforcing biases. Therefore, addressing these perceptions is key to maintaining inclusive bilingual classrooms that recognize language alternation as both a cognitive and affective resource.

Difference in the Attitudes of Respondents toward Code-switching according to Year Level

The succeeding table presents the differences in the respondents’ attitudes toward code-switching when grouped according to their year level (first year, second year, third year, and fourth year).

Table 6. Difference in the Attitudes of Respondents toward Code-switching according to Year Level

Statements	Group Means				F-value	P-value
	1 st year	2 nd Year	3 rd year	4 th year		
1. I converse with my friends using Tagalog and English during our casual conversation.	3.95	3.85	4.07	3.94	1.02 ^{ns}	0.38
2. In my English subject, I speak my own dialect and switch to English from time to time.	3.63	3.67 ^d	3.63 ^d	3.31 ^{bc}	3.99*	0.01
3. As a routine, I mix English and my vernacular language in my English subject because my professor allows me.	3.71	3.73	3.73	3.48	2.13 ^{ns}	0.09
4. During classroom discussion, mixing vernacular language and English language is a good practice among students.	3.78	3.82	3.75	3.52	2.47 ^{ns}	0.06
5. Mixing Tagalog and English can be a means of expressing oneself more easily and more accurately.	4.11	4.11	4.02	3.86	2.02 ^{ns}	0.11
6. Using both Tagalog and English during class discussion makes the learning of English lessons easier and faster.	4.12	4.16	3.96	3.91	1.85 ^{ns}	0.14
7. During group activities, I use a combination of my dialect and English because it is allowed by my teacher.	3.94 ^d	3.98 ^d	3.80	3.63 ^{ab}	2.77*	0.04
8. Combining my dialect and the English language is just natural because it is a linguistic trend being practiced by everyone.	3.91 ^d	4.02 ^d	3.84 ^d	3.59 ^{abc}	3.72*	0.01
9. In using technological gadgets in the school, I prefer using English and Tagalog.	3.94	4.18	3.90	3.85	2.34 ^{ns}	0.08

Legend: a=first year, b=second year, c=third year, d=fourth year

Note: Letter in superscript indicates which group has a significant mean difference.

*Significant ^{ns} Not Significant

The data uncovered significant differences in respondents’ attitudes toward code-switching across year levels. Results showed that second-year students were more likely to use their dialect and switch to English from time to time (M = 3.67; p = 0.01), reflecting both tolerance of ambiguity and varying exposure to English. This maintains Valerio’s (2015)

assertion that Taglish—the combination of Filipino and English—has become a linguistic trend in the Philippines and can even be perceived as a separate dialect. While Taglish is regarded as a cultural trend, the present findings imply that students’ use of dialect-English combinations is not only a sociolinguistic phenomenon but also a pragmatic response to the demands of classroom communication.

Another significant result indicated that second-year students were more inclined to combine their dialect with English because they regarded it as a natural linguistic trend commonly practiced by many ($M = 3.98$; $p = 0.04$), compared to their counterparts. It aligns with Ibrahim et al. (2013), who observed that teachers often code-switch for instructional purposes, particularly to reformulate ideas and facilitate comprehension, although less frequently for explicit language learning. Hence, code-switching helped them express these ideas more clearly, ultimately improving their academic performance.

Furthermore, second-year students frequently used a combination of their dialect and English during group activities, as permitted by their teachers ($M = 4.02$; $p = 0.01$). This suggests that students emphasized that code-switching played a pivotal role in the teaching-learning process, allowing them to comprehend and assimilate complex English lessons more effectively. Since teachers did not impose restrictions against it, students freely mixed their dialect with English to enhance understanding. These findings are consistent with Damaso (2016), who noted that students across different year levels frequently code-switched during English subjects. Hence, this result shows how institutional acceptance (i.e., teachers not restricting it) strengthens students’ view of code-switching as a legitimate classroom practice rather than a fallback strategy.

These findings assert that code-switching functions as both a pedagogical resource and a potential constraint, necessitating a balanced approach that leverages its role in meaning-making while safeguarding the long-term goal of English proficiency.

Table 7. Difference in the Attitudes of Respondents toward Code Switchers according to Year Level

Statements	Group Means				F-value	p-value
	1 st year	2 nd year	3 rd year	4 th year		
1. A student who explains purely in English is more intelligent than one who mixes Tagalog and English during brainstorming.	2.94	2.95	3.16	3.34	2.58 ^{ns}	0.06
2. If I talk to someone who frequently combines his dialect & English, I look at his manner of speaking as a “better speaker” compared to those who purely use his dialect to communicate.	2.48 ^d	2.47 ^d	2.85	2.96 ^{ab}	5.18*	0.01
3. A student who combines Tagalog and English during recitation in his English subject is just being “honest and expressive” about what he really feels.	3.91	4.22 ^{cd}	3.68 ^b	3.84 ^b	4.81*	0.00
4. A student who mixes his dialects and English during brainstorming has poor communication skills.	3.28 ^d	3.40	3.40 ^d	3.84 ^{ac}	4.32*	0.00
5. Code-switchers are also achievers.	3.69	3.82	3.70	3.64	0.66 ^{ns}	0.58

6. Code-switchers should be given additional speaking lessons/drills than those who speak English better.	2.58	2.40	2.53	2.72	1.97 ^{ns}	0.12
7. As a region with several Ilocanos, additional subjects in English must be given by the school to lessen the difficulties in learning English.	3.48	3.82	3.46	3.51	2.41 ^{ns}	0.07
8. Students from the province usually code-switch; unlike in urban places, most students are fluent in English.	2.66	2.40	2.60	2.72	1.60 ^{ns}	0.19

Legend: a=first year, b=second year, c=third year, d=fourth year

Note: Letter in superscript indicates which group has a significant mean difference.

*Significant ^{ns} Not Significant

The outcome further shows significant differences in students' attitudes toward code-switchers when grouped according to year level. Fourth-year students agreed more strongly ($M = 3.84$, $p = 0.00$) that a student who mixes dialect and English during brainstorming has poor communication skills than those in the other levels. It pertains that as students advance academically, they may increasingly view code-switching as a deficiency rather than as a resource. This perception aligns with Saeb and Zamani (2013), who observed that more advanced learners often develop higher expectations for monolingual English competence.

In contrast, second-year students were more favorable toward the idea that code-switching during recitation is an honest and expressive practice ($M = 4.22$, $p = 0.00$). Williams et al. (2019) found that bilinguals often switch languages to express emotions, supporting the interpretation that younger or mid-level students see code-switching as emotionally authentic.

Another significant finding shows that fourth-year students generally agreed ($M = 2.96$, $p = 0.01$) that when they talk to someone who frequently combines dialect and English, they perceive that person as a better speaker compared to those who use only their dialect. This supports Borlongan et al. (2012), who noted that English-Tagalog Code-Switching (ETCS) is widely accepted in universities as a means to enhance understanding of academic content.

Ultimately, fourth-year students stigmatizing code-switchers as poor communicators raises concerns for teacher education. Such attitudes may discourage code-switching in bilingual classrooms, thereby limiting its use as a scaffold for English learning. This highlights the need for teacher preparation programs to reframe code-switching as a legitimate pedagogical tool. Reinforcing policy frameworks like the Bilingual Education Policy and MTB-MLE in higher education is essential to ensure teacher-trainees recognize the instructional value of strategic language alternation.

Difference in the Attitudes of Respondents toward Code-switching according to Courses

The succeeding tables present the data on the differences in the respondents' classroom code-switching attitudes when grouped according to their courses (Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEd), Bachelor of Physical Education (BPEd), Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd), and Bachelor of Technology and Livelihood Education (BTLEd).

It can be drawn that mixing Tagalog and English as a means of expressing oneself showed a significant difference ($p = .04$), with BSEd and BEd students reporting the highest mean ($M = 4.08$).

Table 8. Difference in the Attitudes of Respondents toward Code-switching according to Courses

Statements	Group Means				F-value	p-value
	BEEd	BPEd	BSEd	BTLEd		
1. I converse with my friends using Tagalog and English during our casual conversation.	3.97	3.87	4.02	4.05	1.19 ^{ns}	0.31
2. In my English subject, I speak my own dialect and switch to English from time to time.	3.53	3.68	3.45	3.63	1.30 ^{ns}	0.28
3. As a routine, I mix English and my vernacular language in my English subject because my professor allows me.	3.62	3.75	3.61	3.68	0.50 ^{ns}	0.70
4. During classroom discussion, mixing vernacular language and English language is a good practice among students.	3.71	3.91	3.65	3.70	0.53 ^{ns}	0.66
5. Mixing Tagalog and English can be a means of expressing oneself more easily and more accurately.	4.08	3.98	4.08 ^d	3.77 ^c	2.73 [*]	0.04
6. Using both Tagalog and English during class discussion makes the learning of English lessons easier and faster.	4.11	4.06	3.97	3.95	0.66 ^{ns}	0.57
7. During group activities, I use a combination of my dialect and English because it is allowed by my teacher.	3.83	3.89	3.77	3.79	0.25 ^{ns}	0.87
8. Combining my dialect and the English language is just natural because it is a linguistic trend being practiced by everyone.	3.92	3.83	3.73	3.80	0.81 ^{ns}	0.49
9. In using technological gadgets in the school, I prefer using English and Tagalog.	3.89	3.91	4.02	3.86	0.80 ^{ns}	0.49

Legend: a=BEEd, b= BPEd; c= BSEd, d=BTLEd

Note: Letter in superscript indicates which group has a significant mean difference.

*Significant ^{ns} Not Significant

This result indicates they are more likely than other groups to view code-switching as a helpful strategy for self-expression. Ospanova (2017) similarly noted that code-switching aids learners in simplifying ideas when English alone feels limiting. This highlights code-switching as both a bridge to comprehension and an affirmation of bilingual identity. Thus, its role should be seen not only as a tool for ease of expression but as a nuanced pedagogical practice with both benefits and constraints, depending on how it is applied.

Table 9. Difference in the Attitudes of Respondents toward Code Switchers according to Courses

Statements	Group Means				F-value	p-value
	BEEd	BPEd	BSEd	BTLEd		
1. A student who explains purely in English is more intelligent than one who mixes Tagalog and English during brainstorming.	2.82	3.17 ^c	2.66 ^{bd}	3.13 ^c	4.33 [*]	0.01
2. If I talk to someone who frequently combines his dialect & English, I look at his manner of speaking as a "better speaker" compared to those who purely	3.33	3.42	3.09	3.41	2.30 ^{ns}	0.08

	use his dialect to communicate.						
3.	A student who combines Tagalog and English during recitation in his English subject is just being "honest and expressive" about what he really feels.	3.82	3.72	3.96	3.89	1.15 ^{ns}	0.33
4.	A student who mixes his dialects and English during brainstorming has poor communication skills.	2.63 ^c	2.81 ^c	2.11 ^{abd}	2.86 ^c	9.33 [*]	0.00
5.	Code-switchers are also achievers.	3.61	3.74	3.76	3.66	0.71 ^{ns}	0.54
6.	Code-switchers should be given additional speaking lessons/drills than those who speak English better.	3.41	3.58	3.30	3.59	2.53 ^{ns}	0.06
7.	As a region with several Ilocanos, additional subjects in English must be given by the school to lessen the difficulties in learning English.	3.53	3.62	3.51	3.57	0.26 ^{ns}	0.86
8.	Students from the province usually code-switch; unlike in urban places, most students are fluent in English.	3.50 ^c	3.55 ^c	3.21 ^{ab}	3.48	2.95 [*]	0.03

Legend: a=BEEd, b= BPEd; c= BSEd, d=BTLEd

Note: Letter in superscript indicates which group has a significant mean difference.

*Significant ^{ns} Not Significant

It was further indicated that BTLEd students largely affirm that those who mix dialects and English during brainstorming have poor communication skills ($M = 3.17$, $p = 0.01$), viewing code-switching as a practice of academically weaker students. This contrasts with Abad (2010), who emphasized its role in reducing anxiety and encouraging participation, showing how code-switching can be seen as both supportive and stigmatizing.

In addition, BPEd students believed that explaining purely in English signals greater intelligence than mixing Tagalog and English ($M = 2.86$, $p = 0.00$). While this echoes Saeb and Zamani's (2013) finding that high achievers show more confidence in the target language, it overlooks research demonstrating that strategic code-switching enhances comprehension.

Accordingly, BPEd students generally concurred that provincial students code-switch more often, while urban students are more fluent in English ($M = 3.55$, $p = .03$), reflecting language as a marker of identity. However, Rasouli and Simin (2016) cautioned that frequent teacher code-switching may be read as inadequate proficiency. Without clear rules mandating English use, both teachers and students fall into the practice of code-switching as a norm in classroom interaction.

Difference in the Attitudes of Respondents toward Code-switching according to Native Language (L1)

The following tables exhibit the classroom code-switching attitudes of the respondents when they are grouped according to native language (Iloco, Tagalog, Ibanag, Yogad, Ayangan-Ifugao, Itawes, and Gaddang).

It can be noted in Table 10 an insignificant difference in students' classroom code-switching attitudes when grouped by native language, pointing out that linguistic background does not strongly shape classroom perceptions. It contradicts Valerio (2015), who found that when university students are divided by ethnicity, there is a substantial difference in their attitudes regarding code switching, particularly when they say they converse with their friends in Tagalog and English during casual conversation.

Table 10. Difference in the Attitudes of Respondents toward Code-switching according to Native Language (L1)

Statements	Group Means							F-value	p-value
	Iloco	Tagalog	Ibanag	Yogad	Ayangan-Ifugao	Itawes	Gaddang		
1. I converse with my friends using Tagalog and English during our casual conversation.	3.96	4.03	3.90	4.13	3.57	3.75	3.67	0.60 ^{ns}	0.73
2. In my English subject, I speak my own dialect and switch to English from time to time.	3.53	3.65	3.20	3.63	2.86	3.25	3.33	1.68 ^{ns}	0.13
3. As a routine, I mix English and my vernacular language in my English subject because my professor allows me.	3.65	3.71	3.40	3.63	3.71	3.00	3.33	0.79 ^{ns}	0.58
4. During classroom discussion, mixing vernacular language and English language It is a good practice among students.	3.73	3.67	3.40	4.00	3.71	3.50	3.33	0.64 ^{ns}	0.70
5. Mixing Tagalog and English can be a means of expressing oneself more easily and more accurately.	4.03	4.00	3.80	4.38	3.86	3.25	4.00	1.27 ^{ns}	0.27
6. Using both Tagalog and English during class discussion makes the learning of English lessons easier and faster.	4.05	3.97	3.80	4.25	4.14	3.50	3.67	0.76 ^{ns}	0.60
7. During group activities, I use a combination of my dialect and English because it is allowed by my teacher.	3.84	3.85	3.30	3.88	3.43	3.50	3.33	1.15 ^{ns}	0.33
8. Combining my dialect and the English language is just natural because it is a linguistic trend being practiced by everyone.	3.87	3.76	3.80	4.00	3.00	3.50	3.67	1.50 ^{ns}	0.18
9. In using technological gadgets in the school, I prefer using English and Tagalog.	3.97	3.86	4.20	4.00	3.86	4.25	4.00	0.51 ^{ns}	0.80

Legend: 1=Iloco, 2=Tagalog, 3= Ibanag, 4=Yogad, 5=Ayangan-Ifugao, 6=Itawes, 7=Gaddang

Note: Number in superscript indicates which group has a significant mean difference.

*Significant ^{ns}Not Significant

This emphasizes a key sociolinguistic point that while ethnicity may influence code-switching in informal settings, classroom contexts appear to neutralize these differences, as students focus more on code-switching's functional role in comprehension and participation.

Table 11. Difference in the Attitudes of Respondents toward Code Switchers according to Native Language (L1)

Statements	Group Means							F-value	p-value
	Iloco	Tagalog	Ibanag	Yogad	Ayangan-Ifugao	Itawes	Gaddang		
1. A student who explains purely in English is more intelligent than one who mixes Tagalog and English during brainstorming.	3.10	3.05	3.50	3.88	3.00	3.00	3.13	1.52 ^{ns}	0.17
2. If I talk to someone who frequently combines his dialect & English, I look at his manner of speaking as a "better speaker" compared to those who purely use his dialect to communicate.	2.68	2.72	3.40 ²	2.25	3.71 ²	3.25	3.00	2.71 [*]	0.01
3. A student who combines Tagalog and English during recitation in his English subject is just being "honest and expressive" about what he really feels.	3.91	3.78	3.90	4.38	3.71	3.50	4.33	1.00 ^{ns}	0.42
4. A student who mixes his dialects and English during brainstorming has poor communication skills.	3.52	3.34	3.80	4.13	4.57	3.50	3.33	1.97 ^{ns}	0.07
5. Code-switchers are also achievers.	3.71	3.64	3.60	4.00	3.71	4.25	4.00	0.75 ^{ns}	0.61
6. Code-switchers should be given additional speaking lessons/drills than those who speak English better.	2.52	2.66	2.70	2.50	2.86	2.50	2.33	0.55 ^{ns}	0.77
7. As a region with several Ilocanos, additional subjects in English must be given by the school to lessen the difficulties in learning English.	3.61	3.48	3.50	3.38	3.14	3.50	3.33	0.61 ^{ns}	0.72
8. Students from the province usually code-switch; unlike in urban places, most students are fluent in English.	2.56	2.73	2.70	2.13	2.86	2.50	2.67	0.93 ^{ns}	0.47

Legend: 1=Iloco, 2=Tagalog; 3= Ibanag, 4=Yogad, 5=Ayangan-Ifugao, 6=Itawes, 7=Gaddang

Note: Number in superscript indicates which group has a significant mean difference.

*Significant ^{ns}Not Significant

It was stipulated that students who speak Ayangan-Ifugao are more likely to view speakers who combine their dialect and English as better communicators than those who use only their dialect, with the highest mean (M = 3.40; p = 0.01). This finding is sociolinguistically significant, as it links code-switching with prestige and communicative competence. Also, it means that students may equate bilingual ability with proficiency, shaping how they approach language use in future classrooms.

The use of the students' native language in the EFL classroom has been a contentious issue (Tabaro, 2013), with writers such as Krashen (1981) vehemently opposing it because L2 input is critical for the acquisition process, which can be jeopardized if the mother tongue is used in the L2 classroom. Some academics, on the other hand, advocate for the careful use of the students' native language in the L2 classroom for a variety of reasons, including classroom management and empathy or solidarity communication (Timor, 2012).

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

Based on the outcomes of the study, classroom code-switching is not merely a fallback mechanism but a strategic, context-dependent practice shaped by gender, year level, course, and native language. It stipulates code-switching as a valuable resource for learning, identity, and inclusion, while also exposing tensions in perceptions that link English fluency with intelligence. The study contributes to theory by framing code-switching within the discourse on English as a lingua franca and multilingual education, to practice by highlighting its potential for inclusive pedagogy, and to literature by challenging English-only assumptions.

Consequently, code-switching can be integrated through translanguaging activities, bilingual scaffolding, and structured use of multiple languages to support comprehension without undermining English proficiency. Thus, acknowledging the study's limitations, particularly its cross-sectional scope, recommends the need for qualitative and longitudinal research to capture evolving perceptions, as well as broader contextual analyses to inform language policies that balance proficiency with the communicative and social value of code-switching.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The researchers declare no conflict of interest.

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